

Machine learning-based online monitoring for 3D printing process

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Introduction

➤ Online monitoring for 3D printing

- Avoid human involvements in dangerous scenarios
- Automatic feedback control of 3D printers
- Reduce material waste
- Improve fabrication quality

➤ Machine learning-based image recognition

➤ Questions

How to achieve online 3D printing monitoring via machine learning-based image recognition approach?

General strategy

3D printing data acquisition

Real-time detection

Result

